

NFDI 4
BIODIVERSITY
BIODIVERSITY, ECOLOGY & ENVIRONMENTAL DATA

**Template for the
NFDI4Biodiversity &
iDiv Seasonal School**
Data Management in Ecology and
Environmental Science
2nd - 6th of December 2024

Authors

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Summary

This document describes a one-week course program for a Seasonal School on research data management (RDM) from 2024 which was organised for the second time by partners from the NFDI4Biodiversity consortium. The course aimed to provide young scientists in ecology and environmental science with state-of-the-art skills and knowledge in handling scientific data throughout the data life cycle. Lectures and practical sessions were given by experts from renowned universities, data centers, and research institutions in the environmental research community, covering general aspects of RDM and aspects specifically important for handling ecological data. The participants were introduced to Jupyter notebooks and learned how to combine software tools like Jupyter, R, GitHub, spreadsheet tools, and NFDI4Biodiversity Tools and Services. The course was conducted remotely and targeted PhD students (R1). This publication summarises detailed information about the structure, organisation and lessons learned, and is supposed to be used as a guide for similar events.

Introduction

The amount of data produced in environmental and biodiversity research is rapidly growing, and increasingly large and heterogeneous datasets are used to answer complex questions. Much of the value and reliability of these studies depend on proper data (quality) management and workflows. Consequently, data competence has to develop in pace with modern technologies used in this domain.

Improved research data management allows for efficient spending of public funding by enabling data sharing and reuse, promoting collaborative efforts, and reducing redundancy in data collection. It also contributes to building knowledge by facilitating robust and reproducible research, enabling evidence-based decision-making, and enhancing the transparency and credibility of scientific findings. Consequently, the leading third-party funder in Germany, the German Research Foundation (DFG et al., 2024), incorporated RDM in their mandatory code of conduct “Safeguarding Good Research Practice” (DFG, 2025).

In the context of the biodiversity crisis, high-quality biodiversity data are critical for modelling current trajectories of biodiversity and ecosystem decline, informing policy decisions, and developing effective conservation strategies. By actively participating in research data management and contributing high-quality biodiversity data, ecologists can make a meaningful contribution to the knowledge base of institutions at local to global scales, like local environmental agencies and the expert syntheses of the Intergovernmental Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES).

As more data become available, managing these large and diverse datasets becomes crucial to ensure their usability for future research. This extends to making old data sets available, with the challenge of data integration. For biological data, matching taxonomic information is a specific and essential form of data integration: matching old and alternative names to valid species names and species concepts (Grenié et al., 2022). Handling and analysing large and complex

data sets can be challenging, and usually involves many steps of data cleaning and reformatting. The so-called “executable papers” or reproducible scientific articles, i.e. data, code, analyses, and the manuscript text combined in an executable (Jupyter) Notebook (Jupyter.org, 2025), can improve the transparency and reproducibility of the scientific process (Frank & Hartgerink, 2017; Perkel, 2022) and can be a valuable educational tool (Davies et al., 2020).

To equip researchers with the essential skills to address these challenges, we developed a one-week program for First Stage Researchers (R1) with a background in ecology and environmental sciences.

About the course

Aims of the course

Our aim was to develop a course program specifically for the needs of ecologists, based on open software and free of charge. The NFDI4Biodiversity Seasonal School on Data Management in Ecology and Environmental Science offers theoretical background and practical solutions for day-to-day research data management, combining tools ecologists are already using (e.g. R, Python, Excel) with innovative and interdisciplinary tools (e.g. Jupyter, OpenRefine, RightField, QField). Topics include e.g. metadata standards, data integration, and taxonomic harmonisation, and it uses data and tools provided by partners in the NFDI4Biodiversity network, including plant trait data from the iDiv PlantHub project (iDiv 2025). We further introduce openly available resources for research data management like global biodiversity databases and repositories, and state-of-the-art knowledge about scientific best practices and the legal foundations of handling research data and scientific code.

The course program was developed in close cooperation with lecturers from renowned universities, data centres, and research institutions in the biodiversity community, providing state-of-the-art skills and knowledge in research data management. The course aims to develop skills in handling scientific data along the data life cycle and promotes the use of open teaching formats aligned with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable; Wilkinson et al., 2016).

Learning objectives

The participants learn...

- How to create a data management plan
- How to access data from public databases
- How to collect data with digital tools in the field
- Legal aspects of handling data
- How to integrate (taxonomic) data from different sources
- How to use Jupyter in combination with R (and Python) as a working environment

- How to clean and annotate data
- How to visualise data and FAIR strategies for data analysis
- How to publish data and reproducible code

Target group

We designed this Seasonal School to be as accessible for early career researchers as possible: the course was free of charge, conducted online, and taught in English. In line with the mission of our consortium as a national infrastructure project, we preferred participants from German research institutions, doctoral candidates – preferably in an early stage of their thesis – and with at least a minimum of programming skills in R, Python, or both. We provide a list of [recommended training materials](#) to meet the required level of data handling skills necessary to follow this course. For this second iteration of the course, we further chose to select candidates with similar research topics, i.e. mostly working with terrestrial occurrence data, to increase the homogeneity of the data sets used by the group.

To make sure that practical sessions were effective and every participant was able to ask questions, the number of places was restricted to 20. Applications of members of the iDiv Graduate School, [yDiv](#), were given priority, with about half of the participants belonging to this group. This time, there were more than 80 applications, so unfortunately we could not admit everyone interested in this course.

Course logistics

The course was conducted remotely through Zoom, with English as the primary language of instruction. Everyone involved needed access to a computer with a stable internet connection, a camera, and a microphone.

Each day of the course consisted of two lectures with theoretical aspects and a practical session (see [course program](#)). A total of 13 lecturers were involved, i.e. two to three lecturers per day. We further scheduled two hosts per day, and three hosts for the duration of the five-day course. The organising team consisted of seven people, including one expert who set up the virtual teaching infrastructure. We used Jupyter Notebooks with R and Python kernels in a GFBio-hosted Jupyter instance.

The lecturers prepared slides and Jupyter notebooks or scripts in R or Python. All lecturers agreed to publish their slides and to make a video recording of their lectures available after the course (see [course materials](#)).

Participants were required to create accounts for a number of platforms in advance to be able to follow the course (e.g. GitHub, GBIF/ORCID, QFieldCloud, see [accounts](#)). They were further asked to install the free tools OpenRefine and RightField (Wolstencroft et al., 2011) to be able to join the hands-on session about data annotation ([Practical Session 3](#)). Additionally, participants needed a spreadsheet software to use these two tools (e.g. Excel or LibreOffice). They also

had to download the free QField App on their smartphone or tablet to collect data in the field ([Practical Session 2](#)). These accounts and tools are necessary for any re-use of course materials (see [required and recommended accounts, installations, and tutorials](#)).

We prepared a list of all published teaching materials and recorded lectures (see [course materials](#)) as well as a list of all tools and databases that were used in this course (see [tools and software](#)).

Partners of the NFDI4Biodiversity & iDiv Seasonal School 2024

The second iteration of this course was held on 2-6 December 2024 together with the German Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Research (iDiv) Halle-Jena-Leipzig. The first iteration of this course was the NFDI4Biodiversity & GfÖ Winter School 2022, organised and held together with the Ecological Society of Germany, Austria and Switzerland (GfÖ e.V.) on 5-9 December 2022. This first version of the Seasonal School program is described in detail in Röder et al. (2023).

The following institutions were involved in the preparation and in the implementation of the NFDI4Biodiversity & iDiv Seasonal School 2024:

- Coordination:
 - [German Federation for Biological Data \(GFBio e.V.\)](#)
 - [Philipps University of Marburg](#)
 - [University of Jena](#)
 - [Campus Institute Data Science \(CIDAS\), University of Göttingen](#)
 - [German Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Research \(iDiv\) Halle-Jena-Leipzig](#)
- Technical Infrastructure:
 - [German Federation for Biological Data \(GFBio e.V.\)](#)
- Lecturer Affiliations (alphabetical order):
 - [Campus Institute Data Science \(CIDAS\), University of Göttingen](#)
 - [CICERO Centre for INternational Climate Research, Oslo, Norway](#)
 - [Data Visualization & Information Design](#)
 - [German Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Research \(iDiv\) Halle-Jena-Leipzig](#)
 - [German Federation for Biological Data \(GFBio\)](#)
 - [Global Biodiversity Information Facility Norway \(GBIF Norway\)](#)
 - [Heidelberg Institute for Theoretical Studies \(HITS\)](#)
 - [Leibniz Centre for Tropical Marine Research \(ZMT\)](#)
 - [MARUM - Center for Marine Environmental Sciences](#)
 - [Natural History Museum of the University of Oslo](#)
 - [PANGAEA - Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science](#)
 - [University of Bremen](#)
 - [Leipzig University](#)

About NFDI and NFDI4Biodiversity

The German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) is funded by the DFG to provide access to research data, integrate this data, and make it usable in a sustainable and qualitative manner for the entire German science system. NFDI4Biodiversity is one of a total of 26 NFDI discipline specific consortia, consisting of 50 scientific institutions, museums, natural history societies, state offices, and other institutes and expert groups, providing a wide range of services for handling biodiversity and environmental data. NFDI4Biodiversity offers access to standards, protocols, and formats for data exchange, as well as technical documentation, a data repository search, and the ability to submit data sets and create data management plans according to community standards. The consortium also organises and participates in community events, including training for students and researchers.

Data journey

Figure 1. Overview of tools and training data sets used in the course ([CC BY 4.0](#) figure design by Cédric Scherer, figure content by Juliane Röder).

To emphasize that the lectures align to one common data flow, organizers and lecturers selected training data sets that were used throughout the course. We used three types of training data sets: well curated and documented data sets accessed at discipline-specific repositories, raw data collected by the participants in the field during the course, as well as data that was synthetically rendered uncurated. The clean data sets were used to demonstrate accessing data from repositories, to get to know FAIR tools for processing data (Jupyter, git), and to learn data integration, and data visualization. The data collected by participants during the course was used to introduce tools for digital data collection in the field, as well as data cleaning and curation for data publication.

First, participants learned how to create a data management plan with the GFBio DMP Tool ([Practical Session 1](#)). In this session, participants were encouraged to use an example of their own data/one of their own projects to complete the questionnaire.

Then, participants learned how to discover and access species occurrence data from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) ([Lecture 3](#)). We chose tree occurrences of Fagaceae and Pinaceae in Germany, to restrict the size and spatial extent of the data set. Further, participants were provided with a tutorial on how to access climate data matching the occurrence data set from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts Climate Data Store (EMWFC CDS) (ECMWF 2025) ([Lecture 3](#)). We finally provided participants with trait data for the same tree species from TRY, a global open-access plant trait database (Kattge et al. 2020) ([Lecture 5](#), [Practical Session 4](#)).

A version of the tree occurrence data set with intentional errors was used to introduce participants to reproducible data cleaning of large data sets in OpenRefine ([Practical Session 3](#)).

With two training data sets, the participants learned taxonomic integration of data sets ([Lecture 5](#)). One data set with plant names from the TRY database had been prepared to contain a variety of typical errors found in taxonomic data. Participants learned how to check and correct encoding issues, parse names to optimize later results, and submit data to the GBIF API for name resolution. Afterwards, they repeated these steps for the GBIF tree occurrence training data set, and merged the GBIF and TRY data sets.

The raw data collected by participants during the course was used to introduce the QField App as a tool for digital data collection in the field as a group ([Practical Session 2](#)). The process presented the option for collaborative simultaneous data collection resulting in a single synchronized data set with sampling points from multiple users in different remote locations. The resulting data set showcased typical challenges researchers are confronted with when collecting new data in a group, e.g. different spelling of species names, typos, scientific and vernacular species names, synonyms, missing data, or numbers with erroneously shifted decimal points. The same data set was used to demonstrate the process of data cleaning and data curation necessary to prepare data for publication ([Practical Session 5](#)).

Participants were also trained to use FAIR tools like Jupyter and git ([Lecture 2](#)), data analysis and visualisation according to FAIR principles ([Lecture 7](#)), how to establish reproducible workflows, and how to publish their code ([Lecture 8](#)).

Course program

Day 1 – Foundations of Data Literacy: Navigating Research Data Management & FAIR Principles

Warm-up (60 min)

- Welcome and formalities
- Quick introduction of participants (60 s per person) incl. expectations for the course
- Introduction to NFDI4Biodiversity

Host Dr. Daniel Tschink ([GFBio e.V.](#))
Materials [NFDI4Biodiversity](#) website

Lecture 1 - Research Data Management & Data Literacy (60 min)

- Data life cycle
- NFDI4Biodiversity and GFBio services for data curation

Lecturer Dr. Ivaylo Kostadinov ([GFBio e.V.](#))
Materials [Slides](#) | [Video](#)

Break (10 min)

Lecture 2 - FAIR tools and processes: Getting started with Jupyter & Git(Hub) (90 min)

- Introduction to Jupyter and Quarto
- Introduction to git and GitHub

Lecturer Dr. Johannes Signer ([CIDAS](#))
Tools [Jupyter](#) | [Quarto](#) | [git](#) | [GitHub](#)
Materials [Slides](#) | [Video](#)

Break (50 min)

Practical Session 1 - Create a Data Management Plan (DMP) (120 min)

- DMPs as part of local organisation, for FAIRness and policy compliance
- Parts of a DMP
- Create a DMP based on your research

Lecturers Jimena Linares ([GFBio e.V.](#))
 Dr. Ivaylo Kostadinov ([GFBio e.V.](#))
 Dr. Judith Engel ([University of Bremen](#), [MARUM](#), [GFBio e.V.](#),
 [PANGAEA](#))
Tool [GFBio Data Management Tool](#)
Materials [Slides](#) | [Video Introduction](#)

Wrap-up and outlook (10 min)

Day 2 – Data Collection Day: Data Collection Across Sources

Warm-up (30 min)

- Rehearsal of research data management terms

Host Pascal Scherreiks ([University of Jena](#))
Materials Taboo, list of terms in [supplement](#)

Lecture 3 - Investigating biodiversity data using open-access databases (90 min)

- Introduction to GBIF and how to use GBIF data
- Environmental data types and differences in quality
- Choosing and accessing suitable climate data for ecological analyses
- Combining GBIF and climate data

Lecturer Dr. Erik Kusch ([Natural History Museum of the University of Oslo](#),
[GBIF Norway](#), [CICERO](#))
Tools R package [rgbif](#) | R package [KrigR](#) | [GBIF](#) account | [ECMWF CDS](#)
account | [ORCID](#) account recommended
Materials [Slides](#) | [Tutorial GBIF](#) | [Tutorial Seasonal School 2024](#) | [Video](#)

Break (10 min)

Lecture 4 - Legal aspects in research data management: Data Licensing and Copyright (90 min)

- Data Licensing and Copyright
- Open Source Software licenses
- Creative Commons licenses

Lecturer Uwe Schindler ([University of Bremen](#), [MARUM](#), [PANGAEA](#))
Materials [Slides](#) | [Video](#)

Break (50 min)

Practical Session 2 - Sampling and handling spatial data using QField (120 min)

- Hands-on digital data collection in the field with QField for QGIS app
- Customizing QGIS attribute forms for data collection in Qfield

Lecturer Alexandra Nozik ([ZMT](#))
Tools [QField App](#) | [QFieldCloud](#) account | [QGIS](#) with QfieldSync plugin
Materials [Qfield Official Documentation](#)

Wrap-up and outlook (10 min)

Day 3 – Data Fusion Day: Bridging and Harmonizing Diverse Data

Warm-up (30 min)

- Why don't we share data?

Host Dr. Juliane Röder ([Philipps University of Marburg](#))
Tool [LiaScript Classroom](#)
Inspiration Figure 1 from [Gomes et al. \(2022\)](#)

Lecture 5 - Taxonomic name harmonization (90 min)

- Challenges of working with taxonomic data from different sources
- Name parsing and name resolution with the GBIF taxonomic backbone

Lecturer Dr. David Schellenberger Costa ([iDiv, Leipzig University](#))
Tools R package [rgbif](#) | [Jupyter](#)
Materials [Slides, training data sets & notebooks](#) | [Video](#)

Break (10 min)

Lecture 6 - Data standards (90 min) (cancelled)

Break (50 min)

Practical Session 3 - Data integration & annotation (120 min)

- Step-by-step tutorial for cleaning messy data with OpenRefine
- Step-by-step tutorial for setting up data collection tables with RightField
- Introduction to ReStoRunT

Lecturer PD Dr. Wolfgang Müller ([Heidelberg Institute for Theoretical Studies | HITS](#))
Tools [OpenRefine](#) | [RightField](#) | [ReStoRunT](#) | Spreadsheet software (e.g. [LibreOffice](#), [Microsoft Excel](#), ...)
Materials [Slides & training data sets](#) | [Video OpenRefine](#) | [Video RightField](#) | [Video ReStoRunT](#)

Wrap-up and outlook (10 min)

Day 4 – Data Discovery Day: Unveiling Trends through Data Analysis & Visualization

Warm-up (30 min)

- What are your best and worst experiences with handling data?
- Do you have any data management routines at your working group/institution or for your project? Why not?
- What kind of support would you, as an individual researcher, most urgently need?

Host Pascal Scherreiks ([University of Jena](#))
Materials Research Data Scary Tales - [Biodiversity Edition](#)

Lecture 7 - Data analysis & visualisation according to FAIR principles (90 min)

- Principles of the data science workflow using R and the tidyverse
- Data visualisation principles
- Grammar of graphics with *ggplot2*

Lecturer Dr. Cédric Scherer ([Data Visualization & Information Design](#))
Tools [Jupyter](#) | R package collection [tidyverse](#) (incl. R package [ggplot2](#))
Materials [Slides, code & notebook](#) | [Video](#)

Break (10 min)

Lecture 8 - Publishing your workflow, analysis, scripts using Jupyter, Git and software management tools (90 min)

- How to make scientific code reproducible
- File structure
- Computational environments in R
- How to publish scientific code

Lecturer Dr. Ludmilla Figueiredo ([iDiv](#))
Tools [R](#) | [Binder](#) | [Docker](#) | [GitHub](#) | [Zenodo](#)
Materials [Slides](#) | [Test repository](#) | [Notebook folder structure](#) | [Video](#)

Break (50 min)

Practical Session 4 - Jupyter Hub (120 min)

- Analysing tree occurrence and trait data
- Publishing your scientific code using Jupyter, GitHub and Binder

Lecturer Dr. Johannes Signer ([University of Göttingen](#))
Tools [R](#) | [Jupyter](#) | [GitHub](#) | [Binder](#)
Materials [Training data sets](#) | [Code](#)

Wrap-up and outlook (10 min)

Day 5 – Data Dissemination Day: Sharing Knowledge Through Data Publication

Warm-up (30 min)

- Academic integrity

Host Dr. Juliane Röder ([Philipps University of Marburg](#))

Materials [The Dilemma Game](#), by Erasmus University Rotterdam

Lecture 9 - Data publication & archiving (90 min)

- Benefits of data sharing for individual researchers and for society
- Persistent identifiers (PIDs)
- PANGAEA - the Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Data
- GFBio Data Submission Service

Lecturers Matthias Pauli ([University of Bremen](#), [MARUM](#), [PANGAEA](#))
Dr. Judith Engel ([University of Bremen](#), [MARUM](#), [GFBio e.V.](#), [PANGAEA](#))

Materials Slides part 1 | [Slides part 2](#) | [Video part 1](#) | [Video part 2](#)

Break (10 min)

Practical Session 5 - Publishing data (120 min)

- Preparing data for submission with the PANGAEA Data Curation Checklist

Lecturers Dr. Judith Engel ([University of Bremen](#), [MARUM](#), [GFBio e.V.](#), [PANGAEA](#))

Matthias Pauli ([University of Bremen](#), [MARUM](#), [PANGAEA](#))

Materials [Jupyter Notebook Python](#) | [Jupyter Notebook R](#)

Break (30 min)

Resumée (30 min)

- Open questions
- Feedback
- Link to [anonymous survey](#)

Lessons learned and outlook

An important factor for the success of this Seasonal School was the **intense and productive preparation phase with all lecturers**. We scheduled two meetings with all lecturers and the organizational team, and smaller groups of lecturers organized additional meetings to discuss specific topics, e.g. properties of the training data sets, or shared topics between lectures. This shared effort was crucial for the success of the course.

We invited participants to give feedback on the structure and the contents of the course in two different ways: 1) during the warm-up session on the last day of the course, and 2) via an anonymous survey. **We received valuable feedback** from both approaches.

We received very positive feedback for the **large range and high quality of course topics, and the expertise of the lecturers**. All participants learned some new aspects of research data management that will be useful for their everyday work. The participants further acknowledged the efforts of the organisational team to navigate the absence of some lecturers due to illness. We were able to find a solution for one absence but had to accept another. The high level of expertise of the lecturers limits our options to find suitable backups on short notice.

We were successful in selecting a relatively homogenous group of participants regarding their scientific background and level, which **facilitated exchange among participants about similar challenges in their daily work**. To this end, we included questions about the career status and about programming skills in the application form.

We will adjust advertisements of the course to give a more realistic description of the course structure and contents. We advertised a training scenario with a simulated scientific project throughout the full course but did not live up to this promise (yet). Participants missed this feature, and this was one of the major critiques. We did, however, use common training data sets in this course (see [data journey](#)). We will aim to adjust the course contents to better support our envisioned simulated scientific project. We will further aim to make the data journey more visible and to facilitate participants' transfer of research data management strategies for their projects.

We will improve the management of the course regarding the waiting list and our requirements towards the participants. This time, we did not have a waiting list, so it became a challenge when admitted participants had to step back, and some of the suitable applicants already made other plans, which increased the communication effort necessary to fill all available places. Also, we will communicate more clearly next time that we expect participants to attend the course full-time. If this is not possible, we will encourage application for a later course. We regularly receive a large number of applications for a very limited number of places, and we want to make sure that participants can experience all parts of the course.

We are looking forward to repeating and improving this course!

References

- Davies, A., Hooley, F., Causey-Freeman, P., Eleftheriou, I., & Moulton, G. (2020). Using interactive digital notebooks for bioscience and informatics education. *PLoS Computational Biology*, 16(11), e1008326. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1008326>
- Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft. (2025). *Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice. Code of Conduct*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14281892>
- DFG, Fischer, C., & Güdler, J. (with Dintera, S., Enkler, P., Kaiser, L., Krieger, L., Mrohs, T., Reinhardt, A., & Weigelt, M.). (2024). DFG Förderatlas 2024—Kennzahlen zur öffentlich finanzierten Forschung in Deutschland. <https://foerderatlas.dfg.de>
- ECMWF. (2025). *Climate Data Store*. <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/>, Accessed 2025-06-02
- Frank, M., & Hartgerink, C. (2017). *RMarkdown for writing reproducible scientific papers*. <https://libscie.github.io/rmarkdown-workshop/handout.html> Accessed 2025-06-02
- Grenié, M., Berti, E., Carvajal-Quintero, J., Dädlow, G. M. L., Sagouis, A., & Winter, M. (2022). Harmonizing taxon names in biodiversity data: A review of tools, databases and best practices. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 2041–210X.13802. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13802>
- iDiv.de (2025). PlantHub. <https://planthub.idiv.de>, Accessed 2025-06-02
- Kattge, J., Boenisch, G., Diaz, S., Lavorel, S., Prentice, I. C., Leadley, P., Tautenhahn, S., Werner, G. D. A., Aakala, T., Abedi, M., Acosta, A. T. R., Adamidis, G. C., Adamson, K., Aiba, M., Albert, C. H., Alcantara, J. M., Alcazar, C. C., Aleixo, I., Ali, H., ... Wirth, C. (2020). TRY plant trait database—Enhanced coverage and open access. *Global Change Biology*, 26(1), 119–188. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14904>
- Jupyter.org (2025). Introduction to the JupyterLab and Jupyter Notebooks. <https://jupyter.org/try-jupyter/lab/index.html>, Accessed 2025-06-02
- Perkel, J. M. (2022). Cut the tyranny of copy-and-paste with these coding tools. *Nature*, 603(7899), 191–192. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-00563-z>
- Röder, J., Fischer, M., Tschink, D., & Brand, O. (2023). Template for the NFDI4Biodiversity & GfÖ Winter School. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8221510>
- Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., da Silva Santos, L. B., Bourne, P. E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A. J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C. T., Finkers, R., ... Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3(1), 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
- Wolstencroft, K., Owen, S., Horridge, M., Krebs, O., Mueller, W., Snoep, J. L., du Preez, F., & Goble, C. (2011). RightField: Embedding ontology annotation in spreadsheets. *Bioinformatics*, 27(14), 2021–2022. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btr312>

Supplementary material

A. Course materials

A.1 Lecture slides, Jupyter notebooks, and other materials

- List of Zenodo records: <https://t1p.de/4Biodiv-SeasonalSchool2024>
- Single records (alphabetical order):
 - Engel, J., Linares, J., & Kostadinov, I. (2025). *Publish Biodiversity Data: The GFBio Data Submission and Brokerage Service*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15174063>
 - Figueiredo, L. (2024). *Publishing your (R) workflow: How to get started and where to go next*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14282399>
 - Kostadinov, I., Tschink, D., & Linares Gómez, J. (2025). *Data Management and Data Literacy*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15124025>
 - Kusch, E. (2025). *Investigating Biodiversity Data Using Open-Access Databases*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15097622>
 - Kusch, E. (2024). *NFDI4Biodiversity Seasonal School*. Accessing, handling, and referencing open biodiversity data using the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF). [Accessed 2025-03-31] <https://www.erikkusch.com/courses/gbif/nfdi-download/>
 - Linares, J. (2024). *DMPS as part of local organisation, FAIRness and policy compliance*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14162304>
 - Müller, W. (2024). *Three useful tools to get data in shape* (Version As before held). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14269511>
 - Schellenberger Costa, D. (2024). *Taxonomic name harmonization*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14273559>
 - Scherer, C. (2024). *Data Analysis & Visualisation According to FAIR Principles*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14275834>
 - Schindler, U. (2024). *Legal aspects in research data management: Data Licensing and Copyright*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14268397>
 - Signer, J. (2024). *FAIR tools and processes: Getting started with Jupyter & Git(Hub)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14262125>

A.2 Lecture recordings

- Playlist of all videos: <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL06Unzn1hDrjVAZ0RvNbyQ1Uics9TQ1Kv>
- Single videos (alphabetical order):
 - Engel, J., & Pauli, M. (2025). *Data publication with the GFBio Data submission and Brokerage Service, and with PANGAEA*. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TvSKvLa_b9Q&list=PL06Unzn1hDrjVAZ0RvNbyQ1Uics9TQ1Kv&index=14
 - Figueiredo, L. (2025). *Publishing your (R) workflow: How to get started and where to go next*. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YkuYWzifPdM&list=PL06Unzn1hDrjVAZ0RvNbyQ1Uics9TQ1Kv&index=12>
 - Kostadinov., I. (2025). *Basics of Data Management Planning*. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LyVYrilcpl&list=PL06Unzn1hDrjVAZ0RvNbyQ1Uics9TQ1Kv&index=4>

- Kostadinov, I., Tschink, D., & Linares Gómez, J. (2025). *Data Management and Data Literacy in Biodiversity and Environmental Sciences*.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sbazF7uKVAM&list=PL06Unzn1hDrjVAZ0RvNbyQ1Uics9TQ1Kv&index=2>
- Kusch, E. (2025). *Investigating Biodiversity Data Using Open-Access Databases*. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OelpnrE1r_I&list=PL06Unzn1hDrjVAZ0RvNbyQ1Uics9TQ1Kv&index=4
- Müller, W. (2025a). *Three useful tools to get data in shape - OpenRefine*.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xv7usxUH-Ig&list=PL06Unzn1hDrjVAZ0RvNbyQ1Uics9TQ1Kv&index=9>
- Müller, W. (2025b). *Three useful tools to get data in shape - RightField*.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JRKmyd4RFEo&list=PL06Unzn1hDrjVAZ0RvNbyQ1Uics9TQ1Kv&index=8>
- Müller, W. (2025c). *Three useful tools to get data in shape - ReStoRunT*.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7B0Sg2v02Dc&list=PL06Unzn1hDrjVAZ0RvNbyQ1Uics9TQ1Kv&index=10>
- Pauli, M. (2025). *Data publication and archiving*.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8ujSrpeb0bs&list=PL06Unzn1hDrjVAZ0RvNbyQ1Uics9TQ1Kv&index=13>
- Schellenberger Costa, D. (2025). *Taxonomic name harmonization*.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EbEBKWq5Cxs&list=PL06Unzn1hDrjVAZ0RvNbyQ1Uics9TQ1Kv&index=7>
- Scherer, C. (2025). *Data Analysis & Visualisation According to FAIR Principles*.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iOgdM0atukY&list=PL06Unzn1hDrjVAZ0RvNbyQ1Uics9TQ1Kv&index=11>
- Schindler, U. (2025). *Legal aspects in research data management: Data Licensing and Copyright*. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aqfYvXT4GWo&list=PL06Unzn1hDrjVAZ0RvNbyQ1Uics9TQ1Kv&index=6>
- Signer, J. (2025). *FAIR tools and processes: Getting started with Jupyter & Git(Hub)*. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EQJgigLY9NY&list=PL06Unzn1hDrjVAZ0RvNbyQ1Uics9TQ1Kv&index=2>

A.3 Training data sets

- GBIF.org (25 November 2024). *GBIF Occurrence Download* [Data set]
<https://doi.org/10.15468/DL.GEJVSE>
- Kattge, J., Boenisch, G., Diaz, S., Lavorel, S., Prentice, I. C., Leadley, P., Tautenhahn, S., Werner, G. D. A., Aakala, T., Abedi, M., Acosta, A. T. R., Adamidis, G. C., Adamson, K., Aiba, M., Albert, C. H., Alcantara, J. M., Alcazar, C. C., Aleixo, I., Ali, H., ... Wirth, C. (2020). TRY plant trait database —Enhanced coverage and open access. *Global Change Biology*, 26(1), 119–188. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14904>

A.4 Further materials used in the course

- GitHub repository Seasonal School 2024
<https://github.com/nfdi4biodiversity/SeasonalSchool2024>
- Ransby, D. (2023). *PANGAEA Data Curation Checklist* (Version 0.1.0) [R].
https://github.com/pangaea-data-publisher/community-workshop-material/blob/master/R/Data_curation_checklist/Data_Curation_Checklist.ipynb
- Riemann-Campe, K., & Oellermann, M. (2024). *PANGAEA Data Curation Checklist* (Version 1.2) [Software].

https://github.com/pangaea-data-publisher/community-workshop-material/tree/master/Python/Data_curation_checklist

A.5 Warm-up materials

- Taboo word list
 - research data
 - accessible
 - Nagoya protocol
 - data life cycle
 - open science
 - FAIR
 - version control
 - data management plan
 - Jupyter
 - file naming conventions
 - findable
 - backup
 - cloud storage
 - interoperable
 - SSH key pair
 - 3-2-1 rule
 - reusable
 - repository
 - archiving
 - documentation
 - data base
 - Kernel
- Why don't we share data?
 - Gomes et al. (2022) Why don't we share data and code? Perceived barriers and benefits to public archiving practices *Proc R Soc B* 289: 20221113 <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2022.1113>
- Research data Scary Tales - Biodiversity Edition
 - Röder, J., Frohne, K., & Tschink, D. (2024). Research Data Scary Tales - Biodiversity Edition. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14237417>
- The Dilemma Game
 - Erasmus University Rotterdam. *Dilemma Game*. Erasmus University Rotterdam. Accessed 2025-06-02 <https://www.eur.nl/en/about-university/policy-and-regulations/integrity/research-integrity/dilemma-game>

B. Tools and software used during the course

B.1 Organizing

- Indico (forms and surveys) <https://getindico.io>
- Zoom (web conference) <https://zoom.us>

B.2 Teaching

- Engagement tools
 - Mentimeter <https://www.mentimeter.com>
 - LiaScript Classroom <https://liascript.github.io>
 - Poll.ev <https://www.polleverywhere.com>

B.3 Data management and annotation

- Data Management Plans
 - GFBio Data Management Plan Tool <https://dmp.gfbio.org>
- Data annotation (in spreadsheets)
 - Excel <https://www.microsoft.com/de-de/microsoft-365/excel>
 - LibreOffice <https://www.libreoffice.org>
 - Open Refine <https://openrefine.org>
 - RightField <https://rightfield.org.uk>
 - ReStoRunT <https://github.com/mertova/ReStoRunT>
- Reproducible Coding
 - BinderHub <https://binderhub.readthedocs.io>
 - Docker <https://www.docker.com>
 - Git <https://git-scm.com>
 - GitHub <https://github.com>
 - Jupyter <https://jupyter.org>
 - Jupyter Notebook <https://jupyter-notebook.readthedocs.io>
 - Python <https://www.python.org>
 - Quarto <https://quarto.org>
 - R <https://www.r-project.org>
 - RStudio <https://posit.co/download/rstudio-desktop>

B.4 Databases and data repositories (alphabetical order)

- ECMWF CDS – European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts - access and download data from The Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS) <https://www.ecmwf.int>
- GBIF – Global Biodiversity Information Facility <https://www.gbif.org>
- PANGAEA – Data publisher for Earth & Environmental Science <https://pangaea.de>
- re3data <https://www.re3data.org>
- TRY – Plant Trait Database <https://www.try-db.org>
- Zenodo <https://zenodo.org>

C. Required and recommended accounts, installations, and tutorials

C. 1 Accounts

During the course, we used several services that require personal accounts. Please register with the following services and organizations to be able to re-use the course materials:

Required

- [ECMWF CDS](#) - access and download climate data from The Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS)
 - [How to set up R package *KrigR* with your ECMWF CDS account](#)
- [GBIF](#) - access and download biodiversity data
 - [How to set up R package *rgbif* with your GBIF account](#)
 - alternative: use your GitHub account to sign in to GBIF
 - recommended: connect your ORCID account to your GBIF account
- [GitHub](#) - version control, make your code available
- [Zenodo](#) - publish your code with a DOI
 - alternative 1: use your ORCID account to sign in to Zenodo
 - alternative 2: use your GitHub account to sign in to Zenodo

(Highly) recommended

- [ORCID](#) - self-curated unique researcher ID
 - use ORCID to sign in to Zenodo
 - use ORCID to identify in GBIF
- [QFieldCloud](#) - collect data with [QField](#) app (required during the live course)

C.2 Installations

This is a selection of installation instructions for the tools we used in this course. Participants were asked to install these tools before the course started. Some institutions restrict their employees' ability to install programs on their computers, so this step may take longer than expected. We further recommend the excellent [Carpentries](#) tutorials for git, R, and Python to prepare for the course, as the course program requires at least basic skills in R and Python.

Required

- OpenRefine
 - [How to install and use OpenRefine on various OS \(English\)](#)
- Rightfield
 - [How to install and use RightField on various OS \(English\)](#)
- Spreadsheet software
 - e.g. [LibreOffice](#)
 - e.g. Windows Excel

Recommended

- Git
 - [Introduction to version control with Git, using the command line \(English, Carpentries\)](#)
 - [Optional \(!\) Windows shell for Git](#)

- Jupyter
 - [How to re-use Jupyter Notebooks from the Winter School](#)
 - [How to install Jupyter on your local computer](#)
- Python
 - [How to install Python on various OSs \(English\)](#)
 - [Installing Python with Packages using Anaconda \(English, Carpentries\)](#)
 - [Video Guide to install Python on Windows \(English\)](#)
 - [Video Guide to install Python on MacOS \(English\)](#)
 - [direct link to python.org \(English\)](#)
 - [list of tutorials for beginners on python.org \(English\)](#)
- R
 - [How to install R and RStudio on various OSs \(English\)](#)
 - [Installing R and RStudio \(English, Carpentries\)](#)
 - [Video Guide to install R and RStudio on Windows \(English\)](#)
 - [Video Guide to install R and RStudio on MacOS \(English\)](#)
 - [direct link to RStudio, contains link to R](#)
- QField App (on your mobile phone, required during the live course)
 - [Install the QField App on various OS on your mobile phone](#)

D Application form

We asked applicants about their scientific background, their motivation to join the course, their programming skills, and about their previous experiences with research data management.

- Personal data
 - First Name
 - Last Name
 - Email Address
 - Affiliation
 - yDiv Membership (Yes - No)
 - I would like to receive email notifications about upcoming training events (Yes - No)
- About your studies
 - Field of study (max. 100 characters) - What was the field of study of your highest biodiversity related degree?
 - What is your highest degree in a biodiversity related field of study?
Answers:
 - Bachelor
 - Master
 - PhD

- How many years since you reached this degree? (integer number) - Please count only full years. Finishing your PhD in December 2023 = 0 years. Finishing in May 2023 = 1 year.
- About your research
 - Research topic (max. 100 characters)
 - Letter of motivation (max. 1500 characters)
- About your data
 - Where are your data from?
Answers:
 - I collect data myself
 - I use data sets from other researchers (e.g. open data)
 - What kind of data do you use? (max. 100 characters)
- About your software skills
 - What experience level do you have using R software?
Answers:
 - None (never used before)
 - Basic (I know how to import & handle data)
 - Advanced (I know how to use packages & visualize data)
 - Professional (I am writing & publishing my own scripts)
 - What experience level do you have using Git versioning software?
Answers:
 - None (I never used Git before)
 - Basic (I used it once, but not regularly)
 - Advanced (I know how to use it, but it's not part of my daily routine)
 - Professional (I use it every day)
 - What experience level do you have using Python software?
Answers:
 - None (never used before)
 - Basic (I know how to import & handle data)
 - Advanced (I know how to use packages & visualize data)
 - Professional (I am writing & publishing my own scripts)
- About your data skills
 - Did you already publish data? (Yes - No)
 - Which databases/repositories do you use for publishing data? (max. 100 characters)

- Which databases do you use for searching data? (max. 100 characters)
- Did you ever download open biodiversity data? (Yes - No)
- Which databases/repositories do you use for downloading data? (max. 100 characters)
- Are you familiar with data standards, e.g. Ecological Metadata Language - EML? (Yes - No)

E. Anonymous survey for course evaluation - participants

The first eight questions were single-choice questions, and the last three questions required text answers. We circulated the link to the survey during the warm-up session of the last day of the course, and again in the follow-up email two weeks after the course.

Preparation:

- Would you have liked more information in advance?
Answers: Yes - No

During the Seasonal School:

- ... the aims and structure were clear
Answers: no selection - I do not agree - I rather disagree - I rather agree - I fully agree
- ... the lecturers did use their time pretty well
Answers: no selection - I do not agree - I rather disagree - I rather agree - I fully agree
- ... the lecturers were always open for questions and further assistance
Answers: no selection - I do not agree - I rather disagree - I rather agree - I fully agree
- ... the lecturer showed expertise and were thematically well prepared
Answers: no selection - I do not agree - I rather disagree - I rather agree - I fully agree

In general:

- The time frame of the Seasonal School was appropriate
Answers: no selection - I do not agree - I rather disagree - I rather agree - I fully agree
- How satisfied are you in terms of the Seasonal School?
Answers: no selection - I do not agree - I rather disagree - I rather agree - I fully agree
- Would you recommend the Seasonal School to others?
Answers: Yes - Perhaps - No
- Do you have any suggestions on how we could improve the Seasonal School?
Answers: Text
- Can you name one aspect that you particularly liked?
Answers: Text

- What were your expectations when you attended the workshop? Were they fulfilled?
Answers: Text

F. Anonymous survey for course evaluation - lecturers

The first eight questions were single-choice questions, and the last three questions required text answers. We circulated the link to the survey in an email two weeks after the course, together with first aggregated results of the participants' feedback, and a reminder to upload course materials.

Preparation:

- Would you have liked more information in advance?
Answers: Yes - No

During preparation:

- ... the aims and structure of the Seasonal School were clear
Answers: no selection - I do not agree - I rather disagree - I rather agree - I fully agree
- ... the scope and content of your contribution was clear
Answers: no selection - I do not agree - I rather disagree - I rather agree - I fully agree
- ... more collaboration with other lecturers would have been necessary
Answers: no selection - I do not agree - I rather disagree - I rather agree - I fully agree
- ... an additional meeting would have been necessary to discuss technical support
Answers: no selection - I do not agree - I rather disagree - I rather agree - I fully agree
- ... the organizers were always open for questions and further assistance
Answers: no selection - I do not agree - I rather disagree - I rather agree - I fully agree

During the Seasonal School:

- ... the organizers support was adequate
Answers: no selection - I do not agree - I rather disagree - I rather agree - I fully agree

In general:

- The time frame of the Seasonal School was appropriate
Answers: no selection - I do not agree - I rather disagree - I rather agree - I fully agree
- Contributing to the Seasonal School was a good experience
Answers: no selection - I do not agree - I rather disagree - I rather agree - I fully agree
- Would you recommend contributing to the Seasonal School to others?
Answers: Yes - Perhaps - No

- Do you have any suggestions on how we could improve the Seasonal School (content, structure, logistics)?
Answers: Text
- Can you name one aspect that you particularly liked?
Answers: Text
- What were your expectations when you agreed to support the workshop?
Were they fulfilled?
Answers: Text